

Development of Logo-Cinematherapy Program on the Depression Level and Meaning in Life of the College Inmate Students in Camp Sampaguaita, New Bilibid Prison

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Abstract:- Social exclusion, deprivation of basic rights, absence of freedom, and unfavourable impression of the free society - all these are faced by prisoners of New Bilibid Prison while in detention and completing their prison sentence. In this kind of life situation, loneliness, gloominess, and loss of meaning in life is just a heartbeat away. Pessimistic emotions, unfavourable views about self, experiencing the real situation and scenario of the prison will greatly contribute to depression. Meaning in life is the guiding compass towards a direction in a person's life. Losing it will make someone experience existential vacuum. The researcher used logo-cinematherapy, a combination of logotherapy and cinematherapy, as the treatment modality. Beck's Depression Inventory - 2 and Purpose in Life Test (PILT) were used to select participants; semi-structured interview and focus group discussion results helped determine film selection. The treatment program then underwent pilot testing. Employing the purposive sampling technique, 105 inmate students out of the total population of 236 qualified for the study. Using the Solomon Four-Group Design, eighty students were randomly assigned to four groups. The experimental groups underwent 12 sessions of logo-cinematherapy while those in the control groups availed of and attended the NBP's regular program. The post-test was given to all the groups. Results reveal that logo-cinematherapy is effective in heightening meaning in life and in reducing depression. Control Group 1 also showed increases in meaning in life and reduced depression levels. Control group 2, however, had unclear results in meaning in life and experienced mild to moderate depression. These results showed that the NBP's current programs for inmates, though effective, requires revisiting and enhancement to make it effective for all. Logo-cinematherapy's inclusion in their programs is thus recommended.

Keywords:- College Inmate Students, Depression, Logo-Cinematherapy Program, Meaning in Life.

I. INTRODUCTION

Movie goers, film fanatics, and artist fans are true lovers and ardent viewers of films. In watching movies the aspirations and dream of a person comes true. Movies suspends reality (Sharp, et al., 2002) it makes and allow the viewer to live temporarily in the most perfect world where they always wanted to be. Movies are part of life , it only shows how movies or films affects the viewers. The movie industry and film makings in the Philippines is almost nearing to its curtain down, as observed and seen movies are being viewed in public once a year particularly on Christmas Day as being sponsored by the Metro Manila Development Authority in the event of Metro Manila Film Festival. The decline of movie industry and film making in the Philippines were evident due to the digitalization of the films. Piracy were rampant and widespread in the early 2000's to the later part of 2016, eventually the mass production of android phone and development of phone apps makes movie watching easier through the use phone in anyone's palm. The creation of Viva Max, Net Flix, and Youtube which makes the movie goers decreases and reduces. The soaring of Korean movies and telenovelas also becomes popular and patronize even by the Filipinos. As others claimed that Korea is now being called as the New Hollywood. More so, undeniably that there are some local movies which can be defined or attributed as directed recklessly which causes annoyance to many and leads to patronizing international or foreign produce films as well as artist. Adding to this, is the amount or entrance fee in the movie house which makes the watchers to think if the amount they are paying is worthy of what they will see. The hit of pandemic in the country challenge the entire entertainment businesses. Malls and movie houses were closed, health protocols becomes tighter and strict, location shootings were not permitted unless they will be confined in one area or place which they called as lock in tapings or shootings.

Despite of this, movies have always been considered by people of all ages as a form of relaxation and entertainment. In some instances it makes people cry, laugh, frightened, or fascinated by the stories created by both local and international film makers (Sharp, Smith, and Cole, 2002). Movies are therapeutic and reflective (Berg – Cross

et.al., 1990), the characters and plot of the stories would help a viewer reflect and connect it to his personal life, and the story can makes an audience relate and see himself in the scenario of the movies. Film viewing also reduces the repression and use of defense mechanism (Sharp et.al, 2002). While the characters is a like a mirror that will magnify the expectators where he is in the movie. Movies watched or seen turns to be an inspirational or a guiding compass and motivation to someone who were touch and move by the film. Films can provide a supportive device for understanding maladaptive beliefs and for cognitive restructuring giving clients the motivation to follow through (Wings, 2001).

Some characters of the movies creates an etched or a remarkable performance in the film. Internationally, the character of Dustin Hoffman in Rain Man viewed in 1988, the role of Raymond will always be reminded as a person with Savant Autism, and displayed a high memory person. Tom Hanks in the film Cast Away seen in year 2000, in the role he played as one of the most trusted men in FEDEX as Chuck Norton, trapped and isolated in an island for years but never lost hope and courage that one day he will be out and be saved from his situation, together with his buddy and only bestfriend name as Wilson, he faces the adversities and bravely crossed the ocean to find life and escape from a pacific island. Another inspiring film and characters was being portrayed by Robin Williams in the movie Patch Adams, he is Hunter ‘Patch ‘ Adams, a former psychiatric patient who finds meaning in life during his detention in the facility and realizing that through medical practice he can change anyone and by going against the traditional and most acceptable methods, then he can impart another effective way in caring and curing the patients and that is by applying humor, which in the movie were delighted by some of his colleagues, classmates and patients but hated and rejected by the top most hospital administrator.

Locally and as being used in this study, a veteran and award decorated actor Ronaldo Valdez who played as Capt. Manuel Bonifacio, a former Barangay Captain, widower, and a father to 4 children who were apart due to some personal issues and unsettled differences to his children, the misdiagnosis of lung cancer keep them united and strengthen their bond and union as a family. Piolo Pascual in the role of Gene in the film 9 mornings, his carefree life and philandering affairs were change by the spirit of yuletide season, he was also cast as Mark in the film The Last Night, suicidal in his role due to legal and financial problem, who finds hope out of his imaginary friend named Carmina, who occasionally appear to those people who are getting near of ending their life. Aga Muhlach in his role as Joselito Gopez, an inmate in the death row who were accused of murdering a child, a daughter of an influential and powerful person. Unfortunately despite of his disability he was subjected for execution which makes her daughter promised to acquit his father though decades and years of his death were passed. And Ms. Vilma Santos, as Josie, mother, OFW, and a widow, who tried to align the life of her children derailed due to the death of their beloved father and her absence.

Watching and closely analyzing the film will surely hit a nerve to any viewers, as it reflects and connects to the emotion of the watchers. Indeed, cinematherapy is like bubble bath for the soul (Nancy Peske and Beverly West, 2000 p.xi)

In 1990 when Berg – Cross , Jennings, and Baruch coined the term *cinematherapy* which they defined as a therapeutic technique involving the selection of films for the client to view that will have a direct therapeutic effect to be used as a stimulus for discussion and examination in future therapy session (Wedding and Niemic, 2003). Cinematherapy is a therapeutic intervention wherein therapist selects films pertaining to clients’ issues for them to view or out of session (Berg-Cross et al., 1990) The metaphors are the most important aspect of it, through watching movies the similarity of the metaphor in the film must reflect on their personal life. Sharp et.al (2002) said that cinematherapy is not just watching films but requires an in – depth understanding of the films metaphors, the characters portrayed in the film, and assisting the client in knowing his or her similarities and differences in terms of the film watched.

“ He who has a why to live for can bear with almost any how. “ Frankl, 1969. A known therapist and postulated logotherapy who experienced worst during the time of Nazi regime. He lost everything from his profession, status in the society, and lost his family due to his incarceration for being a member of Jewish family. From the label of being a medical practitioner or physician then it was replaced by prison number. From these detrimental experiences of him he keeps on holding and believing that there is hope out of miserable life situation. According to him, a person does not invent the meaning of his or her own existence, but rather detects it. For Frankl, values, “ do not drive or push a man, but rather pull him “. (Frankl, 1959). This theory of Frankl was used as one of the backbone of the program in this study. By the used of Socratic Method and techniques imbedded in logotherapy, the college inmate students were being exposed and facilitated with them. Logotherapy is a form of existential therapy and a philosophical / psychological system that deals in finding the meaning in life. (Austad, 2007). It is a type of psychotherapeutic diagnosis and treatment that focuses on a “ will to meaning “. Its main goal is to find meaning in one’s life, which is the most motivating force in human experience, also called as existential analysis. (Morgan, 2013).

Man, in an environment where one can freely express ones’ own wants, still strives for more liberation in doing the things he or she wants to do. If a person experiences states of gloom, worry and tiredness in an ordinary environment, how much more if the person was isolated and guarded within the four corners of a prison cell--depression is but a heartbeat away from becoming a reality. Just thinking about how rotten he is, how society makes him feel rejected is enough to affect his view in life. But it is also possible for him to instill in himself the idea that one day, he will be changed and will become useful and productive in the society. People are equally likely to grow, lead

honorable and health-oriented, love, or go in another, less positive direction, which is crooked thinking. Prisoners are also individuals who can take responsibility for their thoughts, feelings and acts relative to the acceptance or non-acceptance of the messages given to them by others.

According to Mahdizadeh, et.al (2016), being uncertain about the purpose or meaning in life, loss of confidence in oneself, and pessimistic views and perceptions about the future are some of the possibilities that will eventually be the underlying factors resulting in depression level, low self – esteem, and increased anger. The application of psychological principles to the correctional facility of the government, New Bilibid Prison has helped in determining and decreasing the destructive effects of depression. The prisoners, like many other people, cope with stress in many ways. Part of their ways of coping are the styles of life which they consistently exhibit. The aforementioned institution offers occupational therapies, leisure and entertainment, crafts-work business, educational facilities and other activities which have helped the inmates prepare themselves towards a better future. Also, these worthwhile pastimes can become more than a hobby for them; as it helps them be able to alleviate their disordered thinking into a strategy with an adaptive value. These are methods of helping the prisoners achieved better adjustment in life through a focus on the here and now procedure.

Being secluded can inject a negative attitude in anyone; how to rise from the breakdown involves a pattern of healthy thoughts accompanied by activity, or else a person may use a maladaptive style which even brings him to the bottom. A better understanding of the prisoners' degree of depression has helped trace the mark of one's reason for living. Giving considerable attention to passive, depressed moments and changing its route to adaptive coping is most needed in the prison community, it is also important to note the success of the college inmates in small ways. Let them see that they are not all failures that they are normal people who matter, have values, know their worth, can feel secure and are able to relate with others.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Setting*

The formal establishment of a National Prisons in the Philippines began during the Spanish regime, when Spanish penal laws contained in royal decrees, ordinances, rules and regulations were extended to the country. The main insular prison was the Old Bilibid Prisons in Manila which was constructed in 1847 and formally opened by a Spanish Royal Decree in 1865. The San Ramon Prison and Penal Farm in Zamboanga City was established in 1870, primarily to confine political offenders. This prison was closed during the Spanish American war.

Under the American regime, more insular prisons and penal colonies were established. The Iwahig Penal Colony in Palawan was created on November 16, 1904. The San Roman Prisons, which was closed in 1898, was reopened. The Reorganization Act of 1905 created the Bureau of

Prisons effective November 1 of the same year and placed it under the Department of Commerce and Police. Then it was transferred to the Department of Public Institution. The Prison Law which was enacted pursuant to the provision of sec. 1705 – 1751 of the Administrative Code of 1917, finally placed the Bureau of Prisons under the Department of Justice. The three prisons and penal colonies, i.e., old Bilibid, San Ramon, and Iwahig, were placed under the Bureau of Prisons including the Corregidor Stockade and the Bontoc Prison which were later phased out.

Due to increasing inmate population and criminality, more prisons and penal colonies were created and placed under the supervision of the Bureau; the Correctional Institution for women in Mandaluyong, Rizal was established on January 21, 1932 in accordance with Act no. 3732 and Proclamation 414 series of 1931; and the Old Bilibid Prisons was transferred to its present site in Muntinlupa in 1936 and renamed the New Bilibid Prison in 1941.

Under the Philippine Republic after World War II, two or more prisons were created to decongest the over crowded condition of the New Bilibid Prisons. The Sablayan Penal Colony in Mindoro Occidental and Leyte Regional Prisons were established on September 27, 1954 and January 16, 1973, respectively. To date, there are seven major correctional facilities in the country.

PD 28 dated October 25, 1972 establishes the Regional prisons and converts existing national penal institutions prisons and penal farms while PD 29, dated October 25, 1972 amended subparts (d) of Sec. 1735 and subparts (b) of Sec 1740 of the Revised Administrative Code. PD. 139 dated May 1973, provides for an additional regional prisons in Cebu.

As provided for in the New Administrative Code of 1987, Sec 26, the name of the Bureau of Prisons was changed to Bureau of Corrections in 1989 and focused on the rehabilitation function of the Bureau . (Morales ,2003)

➤ *Participants*

In this study the college inmates students from the education department managed by the University of Perpetual College Rizal DALTA in Medium Security Camp. They are presently enrolled at the degree of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Entrepreneurship. All of them are males, adults, and proven guilty beyond reasonable doubt by the competent court of the Philippines.

➤ *Test Instruments*

The researcher used two psychological test, that measures the variables in this study. Becks Depression Inventory – 2, a test that measures depression level and for meaning in life, Purpose in Life was utilized. . Below are the brief description of the tests.

➤ *Becks Depression Inventory 2*

The Beck Depression Inventory II (BDI – II) is a self-report measure consisting of 21 items, which assess the intensity of the emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and somatic symptoms, characteristic of depression. It is used not only to establish the baseline for the depressive complaint, but also to evaluate the various contributing problems that combine constitute the complaint. Moreover, the BDI – II has sound specificity and sensitivity (Sharpley and Bitsika, 2014). Brouwer, Meier, and Zevalking (2013) established that the total BDI score reflects a single construct and that reporting and interpreting individual subscale scores may result in misleading conclusions. According to the BDI, higher scores indicate an increase in the depression and lower scores signify a decrease in depression.

➤ *Purpose in Life Test*

This instrument was constructed by J.C. Crumbaugh and L.T. Maholick (1962 – 1969). As written in the Manual of Instruction for the Purpose in Life Test (1969), this test is an attitude scale constructed from the orientation of Logotherapy (Gr. Logos meaning; logotherapy; treatment through finding meaning in life). The authors wrote that it is intended to ascertain of Frankl's basic concept the, "existential vacuum," or a failure to find a meaning and purpose in life – a "state of emptiness, manifested chiefly a by boredom." This instrument was used to detect the presence of that "existential vacuum." This test contains three parts, namely, Part A is made up of 20 items rated on seven point scale wherein the examinee is asked to encircle the number of each statement that is most nearly descriptive of him; Part B has 13 incomplete sentences wherein the examinee is instructed to complete the phrases with the first thing that comes into his mind. Part C is a writing assignment on personal aims, ambitions, goals in life and the progress made by achieving these.

➤ *Procedures*

The study focuses on the combination of the two known and established therapies, Logotherapy and Cinematherapy. Focus Group Discussion were facilitated to the members of the student council. A group discussions were held to determine the inner most emotions and perceptions of the student inmates towards to the questions given which reflects their present status as inmate and students of the college department. The program were prepared, conceptualized, and written by the researchers. After which 4 evaluators studied, reviewed, graded, and evaluated. After following the revisions and receiving an approval to them, the program which he called as Logo-cinematherapy was pilot tested to 8 participants, randomly selected to determine the effect and to know the points of improvement. The pilot testing was started with a pretest coming from the entire population, the said participants came from the entire population. To start the intervention 2

sessions of Establishing Rapport were performed for them to feel comfortable and at ease with the researcher. 12 sessions were given to the pilot testing groups. In every session a movie is being watched by them and a Socratic Method is used in discussing for the processing of the session. A journal writing is an assignment given to them and will be submitted on the next meeting. A week after the last session, a post test is given to determine the effect whether the program was effective or not. The computation shows that the depression level reduces and move them to normal or having no depression at all. While the meaning in life from having an existential vacuum of clear meaning in life. In addition, an interview was also conducted to the teachers and administrators of the school, the purpose of this is to determine the views of them with regards to the present emotion and psychological state of the inmates based from their personal experiences with them.

Revising some of the procedures, questions, and improving in giving some related examples, the researcher plotted the date and time for the actual group for Experimental Groups 1 and 2. While the Control Groups 1 and 2 will avail the program of NBP but not to attend any Logo-cinematherapy sessions simultaneous with the Experimental Groups. From the total population (320 students) of college inmates students, the researcher facilitated the pretest to them using the two test (BDI-2 and PILT). Using the Purposive Sampling Technique, the participants are carefully selected and chosen, to qualify the participants must have double negative interpretation meaning (1) Experiencing depression either in three levels either mild, moderate, or severe. (2) Having an existential vacuum or unclear meaning in life. An interpretation of normal in depression and an indecisive meaning in life or clear meaning in life will make a student unfit to participate in the study. Although one of the interpretation is positive and the other one is negative, still the student will not be qualified. There are 98 qualified students to be participants in the study. Fishball technique was used in assigning the participants into 4 groups namely (Experimental Groups 1 and 2 and Control Groups 1 and 2). After the random assignment, the 1st session was being plotted and schedule. As permitted, the sessions were slated every Tuesday and Thursday from 10am to 2pm. Same with the pilot testing group, the session started with Establishing Rapport for 2 sessions. And the 12 sessions is for the facilitation of Logo-cinematherapy. Film viewing, Socratic Methods, Processing, and Journal Writings were also performed for the actual groups. The post test for the 2 test were also conducted to Experimental Group 1 followed by the Control Group 1. The next batch or the Experimental Group 2 followed. Same procedures and programs was used and a post test for this group together with the Control Group 2.

Computations and statistics were performed to determine the effectivity of the program.

III.RESULTS

Employing different statistical treatments to determine the validity and effectivity of the program development. The following are the tables and results including the explanation of it.

Table 1 illustrates the demographic profile of the participants in terms of age, civil status, crime committed, and length of sentence. Frequency and percentage is being used in presenting the data.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distributions of the Participants when grouped according to Age, Civil Status, Crime Committed, and Length of Sentence.

Demographic Profile	Variable	Experimental Group N = 40	Control Group N = 40	Frequency	%
Age	25 – 30	5	7	12	15
	31 – 40	11	11	22	27.5
	41 – 50	11	15	26	32.5
	51 – 60	9	7	16	20
	61 – 70	4	0	4	5
	Total	40	40	80	100
Civil Status	Single	21	14	35	43.75
	Married	16	17	33	41.25
	Seperated	3	8	11	13.75
	Cohablitating	0	1	1	2.5
	Total	40	40	80	100
Crime Committed	Against Person	37	39	76	95
	Against Property	3	1	4	5
	Against Public Order	0	0	0	0
	Total	40	40	80	100
Length of Sentence	1 – 10	13	16	29	36.25
	11 – 20	17	19	36	45
	21 – 30	1	0	1	1.25
	31 – 40	9	5	14	17.5
	Total	40	40	80	100

Table1 illustrates the demographic profiles of the participants. They are classified into four (4) categories such as their age, civil status, crime committed, and length of sentence. Considering the age group of the participants most of them are in the ages between 41 – 50 years old, 26 (32.5 %)closer to that is the age between 31 – 50 years, 22 (27. 5%), while very few of them are classified as senior citizen, 4 (5%). In civil status most of them are either single, 35 (43.75 %) or married, 33 (41.25 %). Only 1 member of the groups attested that he is cohabitating (2.5 %). In the crime committed almost all of them violated crimes referring to crime against person, 76 (95%), none of them were imprisoned due to crime against public order, 0. Many of them where sentenced between 11 – 20 years of imprisonment , 36 (45%) while 29, (36.25 %) needs to languish between 1 to 10 years. While 14, (17.5 %) where meted a prison length of Reclusion Perpetua or life imprisonment with a numerical value of 30 years and one day to 40 years.

Table 2 Shows the Pretest and Posttest Mean Score of the 8 Participants in Terms of Depression Level and Meaning in Life Pilot Testing Group Test Result in Terms of Depression Level and Meaning in Life

Variable	Pre Test	Interpretation	Posttest	Interpretation
Depression Level	25.3 Moderate	Moderate Depression	12.9 Normal	Normal
Meaning In Life	81.6 Unclear	Unclear Meaning In Life	114.2 Clear Meaning In Life	Clear Meaning In Life

Table 2 displays the men score result of the pilot testing group. It shows that the depression level and meaning in life of the group is negative, which means they are suffering from moderate depression and also experiencing unclear meaning in life. After the sessions, it reflects that their the two variables improves to a normal range. Which indicates the success of the program given to the participants.

Table 3 shows the results of Pretest and Post test of Purpose in Life Test. Computing the mean scores and standard deviation of the 4 groups.

Table 3 Pretest and Post Test Mean Scores and Standard Deviations in the Meaning in Life of the 4 Groups

Groups	Pretest	Standard Deviations	Post Test	Standard Deviations
A. Experimental Group 1	80.3 Unclear	13.08	95.4 Indecisive	17.85
B. Control Group 1	84.1 Unclear	9.57	95.85 Indecisive	9.69
C. Experimental Group 2	-----	-----	95.85 Indecisive	22.48
D. Control Group 2	-----	-----	90.05 Unclear	16.06

Table 3 shows the pretest and post test means scores and standard deviation of the 4 groups in terms of meaning in life. The Experimental Group 1 has a pretest mean score of 80.3 which is classified as unclear meaning in life, with a standard deviation of 13.08, the post test mean score of 95.4 interpreted as indecisive meaning in life and a standard deviation of 17.85. The Control Group 1 has a pretest of 84.1 or defined as unclear meaning in life with a standard deviation of 9.57, in posttest the mean score is 95.85 or indecisive meaning in life and a standard deviation of 9.69. The Experimental Group 2, has a mean in the pretest of 95.85 and a standard deviation of 22.48, while the Control Group 2 who remains in unclear meaning in life with a mean score of 90.05 with a standard deviation of 16.06.

The pretest mean score showed unclear meaning in life in Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1. The post revealed the interpretation of indecisive for Experimental Group 1, Control Group 1, and Experimental Group 2. While the Control Group 2 remain unclear. It displayed that the logo-cinematherapy is effective, while the NBP Program works effectively in Control Group 1, but failed to Control Group 2.

Table 4 shows the results of Pretest and Post test of Becks Depression Inventory - 2. Computing the mean scores and standard deviation of the 4 groups.

Table 4 Pretest and Post Test Mean Scores and Standard Deviations in the Depression Level of the 4 Groups

Groups	Pretest	Standard Deviations	Post Test	Standard Deviations
A. Experimental Group 1	20.05 Moderate Depression	6.47	11.95 Normal	7.92
B. Control Group 1	19.3 Mild Depression	4.85	13.55 Normal	57.57
C. Experimental Group 2	-----	-----	13.4 Normal	8.52
D. Control Group 2	-----	-----	17.15 Mild Depression	9.77

Table 4 explains the pretest and post test mean scores and standard deviation in terms of depression level among the 4 groups. The Experimental Group 1 has a mean score of 20.05 or moderate depression, with standard deviation of 6.47, while the post test score of 11.95 indicates that they have minimal level of depression or almost no depression experience at that time. In the Control Group 1, the result of the pretest is 19.3 or mild depression and a standard deviation of 7.92. In Experimental Group 2, the post test score revealed that they have minimal or acceptable level of depression, 13.4. While the standard deviation 8.52, While in Group 2, the depression level in mean score of the post test remains to be depressed as they are classified experiencing mild depression with a standard deviation of 9.77.

The pretest mean score in depression level is moderate (Experimental Group 1), mild (Control Group 1) and moves to normal in the posttest, same result yields to Experimental Group 2. While the Control Group 2 remain in Mild depression after being measured. It shows that the Logo-cinematherapy is effective in decreasing the depression of the participants, while the NBP program does not encompasses effectivity to all in terms of decreasing or reducing the depression of the inmates.

Table 5 displayed a significant difference between in the pretest and post test scores in the meaning in life of the 4 groups. T – test of independent mean or uncorrelated for Comparisons of Groups in the Pretest and Post test of Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 1 vs. Control Group 1. T – test of dependent mean or correlated for Experimental Group 1, Control Group 1, and Experimental Group 2 vs. Control Group 2, also in terms Pretest and Post test.

Table 5 Significant Difference on the Pretest and Post Test Scores in the Meaning in Life of the 4 Groups

Comparison of the Groups	Pretest	Posttest	Computed Value	Tabular Value	Decision	Effect Size	Interpretation
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	Yes	-----	1.02	2.032	Accept Ho Insignificant	---	-----
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	-----	Yes	0.06	2.032	Accept Ho Insignificant	---	-----
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	Yes	Yes	10.1	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.83	Large Effect
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	Yes	Yes	9.60	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.81	Large Effect
Experimental Group 2 Vs. Control Group 2	-----	Yes	2.31	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.20	Very Small Efeect

Table 5 shows the comparison of groups in terms of meaning in life. The first comparison is between Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1. The pretest mean score were compared and it shows that the tabular value (2.032) is greater than the computed value of 1.02. The null hypotheses is accepted which means it is insignificant. With the same groups comparing their posttest mean score results, the computed value of 0.06 is lesser than the tabular value of 2.032, in which the null hypotheses is accepted as it implies insignificant. The Experimental Group 1 examining the effect of logotherapy with them it displayed significant effect with a computed value of 10.1 and the tabular value of 2.032 which the null hypotheses is rejected and connotes significance. The computed effect size of 0.83 gives an interpretation of large effect of the program to this group of participants. The Control Group 1 as to determine if their meaning in life improves based from the program given by the NBP, using the pretest and posttest scores, the computed value is 9.60 and the tabular value of 2.032 which it rejects the null hypotheses and indication of significance of the program of NBP in terms of their meaning in life. The computed effect size of large, signifies that the program of NBP top this group is effective. The comparison of groups between the Experimental Group 2 and Control Group 2 considering the result of the post test coming from these two groups, the computed value is 2.31 with the tabular value of 2.032 which indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected which showed significance and the effect size is very small.

In the comparisons of the groups between Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1, the pretest scores of Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1 showed insignificant or it means that they almost have the same level in meaning in life before the intervention or treatment. In the groups between Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1, the post test scores shows insignificant which means that the logo – cinematherapy and NBP Programs are both effective in alleviating the meaning in life. In the Experimental Group 1 as measured in pretest and posttest in meaning in life. This group who undergo logo-cinematherapy showed increase in alleviating in meaning in life. It has a large effect as to compare the result of their pretest against the post test . In the Control Group 1, who undergo the regular program of NBP showed increase in meaning in life. From unclear meaning in life to indecisive. The effect was also large in effect, as to compare their pretest to post test. In the groups between Expeoirmental Group 2 and Control Group 2, as to compare their post test scores result, it shows that there is a small effect on the two group in terms of logo – cinematherapy and NBP Programs. The NBP Programs failed to take effect on Control Group 2 in meaning in life.

Table 6 displayed a significant difference between in the pretest and post test scores in the depression level of the 4 groups. T – test of independent mean or uncorrelated for Comparisons of Groups in the Pretest and Post test of Experimental Group 1 and Experimental Group 1 vs. Control Group 1. T – test of dependent mean or correlated for Experimental Group 1, Control Group 1, and Experimental Group 2 vs. Control Group 2, also in terms Pretest and Post test.

Table 6 Significant Difference on the Pretest and Post Test Scores in the Depression Level of the 4 Groups

Comparison of the Groups	Pretest	Posttest	Computed Value	Tabular Value	Decision	Effect Size	Interpretation
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	Yes	-----	0.57	2.032	Accept Ho Insignificant	-----	-----
Experimental Group 1 Vs Control Group 1	-----	Yes	0.57	2.032	Accept Ho Insignificant	-----	-----
Experimental Group 1	Yes	Yes	14.79	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.91	Large Effect
Control Group 1	Yes	Yes	4.99	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.54	Medium Effect
Experimental Group 2 Vs. Control Group 2	-----	Yes	3.35	2.032	Reject Ho Significant	0.98	Large Efeect

Table 6 shows the comparison of groups in terms of depression level. The first comparison between Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1 in their pretest scores showed that the computed value of 0.57 is lesser than the tabular value of 2.032 which means it accepts to null hypotheses and same results yields to their post test using the same groups, whose computed value is in the same value of 0.57 which also accepts the null hypotheses. Examining the pre test and post test scores of the Experimental Group 1, the computed value of 14.79 and with a tabular value of 2.032, the effect size (0.91) which means a large effect on the program they received. For the Control Group 1, the pretest and post test displayed a result of 4.99 for computed value with a tabular value of 2.032 which means the null hypotheses is rejected. The effect size (0.54) which means a medium effect on the program of NBP to the inmates who belongs to this group. The groups of Experimental Group 2 and Control Group 2 in the post test scores reflects a computed value of 3.35 and the tabular value is 2.032 which resulted to the rejection of the null hypotheses with an effect size of 0.98 which means a large effect in the result.

In the comparisons of groups between Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1, the pretest scores showed it has almost the same level of depression before the exposure of the groups either in logo-cinematherapy and NBP Programs. The posttest scores of Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1 is almost the same, both groups are normal in depression. It shows that the Logo-cinematherapy and NBP Programs are effective in reducing or normalizing the depression. The Experimental Group 1, who undergo logo – cinematherapy displayed effectivity. Their depression level becomes normal after participating in the 12 sessions. It shows large effect in terms of pretest to post test result. The Control Grpup 1 reduced their depression and move to the normal level, after going to the NBP Programs. The effect of this was in medium as to compare the result of the pretest and post test results. The depression level of Expeirmental Group 2 and Control Group 2 has a large effect in the depression level. The Expeirmental Group 2 becomes normal after logo-cinemetherapy while the Control Group 2 failed to have a normal depression.

Table 7 explains the effectivity of the logo-cinematherapy in the depression level of the participants.

Table 7 Effectivity of Logo-Cinematherapy Program on the Depression Level of the Two Groups

Groups In Logo-Cinematherapy	Pretest	Posttest
Experimental Group 1	20.05 Moderate Depression	11.5 Normal
Experimental Group 2	-----	13.4 Normal

Table 7 explains the result of the pretest and post test mean scores of the two groups who undergo logo-cinematherapy. The Experimental Group 1 showed a mean score of 20.05 for pretest which means moderate in depression level while the Experimental Group 2 is also classified as a group suffering from depression. After sessions and participation in Logo-cinematherapy, the depression of the participants both in the two groups becomes normal, as the post test reveals that it is 11.5 for the Experimental Group 1 and 13.4 for Experimental Group 2. Which the two mean scores has an interpretation of Normal or Minimal Depression.

The result of this table clearly explains that the program created for them particularly the logo-cinemetherapy is effective in decreasing the level of depression experienced by the students

Table 8 explains the effectivity of the logo-cinematherapy in the meaning in life of the participants.

Table 8 Effectivity of Logo-Cinematherapy Program on the Meaning in Life of the Two Groups

Groups In Logo-Cinematherapy	Pretest	Posttest
Experimental Group 1	80.3 Unclear Meaning In Life	95.4 Indecisive
Experimental Group 2	—————	95.85 Indecisive

Table 6 shows the effect of logo-cinematherapy program on the meaning in life to the 2 groups of participants. The Experimental Group 1 pretest showed a mean score of 80.3 which means unclear meaning in life while it shows the same result for the Experimental Group 2 who also experienced the same meaning in life. After sessions of logo-cinematherapy the post test mean score showed an increase to Experimental Group 1, 95.4 which means Indecisive while 95.85 which also has an interpretation of Indecisive for Experimental Group 2.

The program of logo-cinematherapy displayed significant effect on the meaning in life of the participants. The participants of the two groups have perceiving somehow a clear meaning in life after actively participating in the program. Although they are not totally move out from the unclear meaning in life to a clear meaning in life but then the post test results suggest that the program itself can assist them in having a better meaning in life.

IV. DISCUSSION

The participants of the study are all interpreted having double negative interpretation. They are depressed which varies in intensity either mild, moderate, or severe. At same time, they are also seen having unclear meaning in life or existential vacuum. From the entire population of the college department in Camp Sampaguita, the pretest were facilitated and out of 320 students 98 of them are qualified with the set criterion of two negative interpretation. The 8 participants were randomly chosen to be a member of pilot testing which is composed of 2 sessions for Establishing Rapport and 12 sessions for Logo-cinematherapy, then the post test is given after a week from the last session. The post test mean score for the 2 test shows that they reduced and eradicated depression which gives them an interpretation of normal while their meaning in life changes and turns to be indecisive. Based from the results and observations from the dry run of the program

Some revisions and improvements are made to make the program suited and fitted for the participants in the actual group. It shows that the program logo – cinematherapy is effective to the small group of population.

The actual group were composed of 4 groups to comply for the research design of Solomon 4 Group. Using the sampling technique of Purposive Sampling Technique, 80 individuals were assigned randomly into the groups. Which has a total of 20 participants in each group. Same with the pilot test group, they undergo 2 sessions of Establishing Rapport, part of these is the introduction of the researcher to them and same with the participants who also introduce themselves. 12 Sessions of Logo-cinematherapy

were facilitated to them, after watching discussions were followed using the Socratic Method. In each sessions questions about the films and themselves were being discussed and they share their answers and perceptions with each other. At the end of the sessions an assignment were given to them to for them to fully understand and internalize the movie seen and the logotherapy facilitated. Post test were also given to the two experimental groups after which the control groups were also given the post test of the two tools (BDI-2 and PILT).

Computation and statistics shows that the demographic profile of the participants respecting at their age, civil status, crime committed, and length of sentence. Most of the participants in their age ranging from 41 to 590 years old 26(32.5%) and only 4(5%) of them are senior citizen age ranging 61 to 70 years old. In civil status, most are single 35 (43.75 %) and only 1 (2.5%) are cohabitating. Majority of them were imprisoned due to crime against person 76(95%). As per court decided meted there imprisonment 36(45%). While 29(36.25%) are sentence to be imprison from 1 to 10 years. The pretest and post test in terms of meaning in life as measured by the PILT showed that the mean score in the pretest of the 4 groups are all unclear meaning in life after the sessions of logo-cinematherapy to the two Experimental Groups their mean scores increases, Experimental Group 1, 95.4 (SD= 17.85), and for Experimental Group 2, 95.85 (SD = 22.48). The Control Groups where continuously availing the NBP programs, the Control Group 1 has a mean score of 95.85 (SD = 9.56), and for Control Group 2, 90.05 (SD = 16.06) which indicates that this group (CG2) remains to be in Unclear Meaning In Life. Referring for the depression level of the participants as measured by the BDI – 2, it shows that the 4 groups as reflected that they are depressed either in mild, moderate, or severe level. After the sessions of logo-cinematherapy, a post test is given and the two experimental groups revealed that they are moved to normal level. The mean score of the Experimental Group 1, 11.95 (SD = 7.92), and for Experimental Group 2, 13.4 (8.52). The Control Groups who failed to experience the logo-cinematherapy, showed that the Control Group 1, 13.55(57.57) who were move to normal range, and for Control Group 2, who remains to be depressed under mild depression with a mean score of 17.15 (SD = 9.77).

Examining the significant difference between the pretest and post test of the 4 groups. It shows that the comparing the pretest result of Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1 from the computed value of 1.02 and the tabular value of 2.032, which the null hypotheses is accepted which means insignificant it also explains that the program has no effect to the participants since it haven't started when the pretest for meaning in life is given. Comparing the post

test of the same groups (EG1 and CG1) the computed value of 0.06 is lesser than the tabular value which means the null hypotheses is accepted or the result is insignificant, this happened due to the positive effect of the program logo – cinematherapy on the Experimental Group 1 and for the Control Group 1 who availed the existing NBP Programs. While Experimental Group 1 as to test the significant difference in terms of pretest and post test the computed value of 10.1 is greater than tabular value of 2.032 which means that the null hypotheses is rejected and has a significant large effect. It shows that the program that they received was effective in assisting to perceive a clear meaning in life. Although they were interpreted with an interpretation of Indecisive though they are not totally moved out but the increase of score after the execution of the program is a sign of success in the program created. The Control Group 1 who has a computed value of 9.60 in terms of the pretest and post test as to determine the significant difference of the program, since the tabular value of 2.032 is lesser than the computed value the null hypotheses is rejected and displayed a significant large effect which indicates the positive effect of the NBP program to the participants. Testing the significance difference of Experimental Group 2 and Control Group 2 in terms of their post test result the computed value of 2.31 is greater than 2.032 which the null hypotheses is rejected with a significant very small effect that implies the unsuccessful result of NBP programs to the Control Group 2 whose meaning in life stayed to be unclear as to compare to the Experimental Group 2 whose meaning in life progress and interpreted as Indecisive after receiving a treatment of Logo-cinematherapy.

The depression level of the 4 groups were also assessed to determine their significant difference. The pretest of the Experimental Group 1 and Control Group 1 which has a computed value of 0.57 against the tabular value of 2.032, the computed value is lesser than the tabular value, which makes the null hypotheses is accepted, it shows that the absence of logo-cinematherapy would suggest that there will be no progress in the depression level of the inmates. The computed value and tabular value in terms of the post test of the two groups (EG1 and CG1), the null hypotheses is accepted or insignificant which means that the two groups experienced positive effect which reduces their depression and resulted to normal range. The pretest and post test of the Experimental Group 1, has a computed value of 14.79 and has a tabular value of 2.032 which means the null hypotheses is rejected, or significant large effect. It shows that the program given or logo-cinematherapy is effective to the Experimental Group 1. The Control Group 1, in the pretest and post test displayed that the computed value of 4.99 with the tabular value of 2.032, it rejects the null hypotheses, a significant medium result after they were exposed in the NBP programs. The Experimental Group 2 and Control Group 2 has a computed value 3.35 and a tabular value of 2.032, since the computed value is greater than the tabular value which the null hypotheses is rejected, the significant large effect can be detected in the success of the logo-cinematherapy to the Experimental Group 2 while the NBP Programs for Control Group 2 fails as they

experienced depression despite of being exposed to the existing program of NBP.

The success of the logo-cinematherapy program given to the actual groups or Experimental Group 1 and 2 can be seen in their mean score of the test PILT for meaning in life, it reveals that after the sessions Experimental Group 1 had a computed group value of 95.4 which indicates an Indecisive interpretation which that somehow they were able to perceive a meaning in life out of the program facilitated to them. Same interpretation yields to the Experimental Group 2 who marked a mean score of 95.85 after participating in the program given. While the depression level they had also reduces to a normal range. The Experimental Group 1 had a mean score of 11.5 and for the Experimental Group 2 is 13.4.

The results of the two actual experimental groups magnify the outcome of the pilot testing participants. Whose depression level and meaning in life improves after actively participating in the logo-cinematherapy sessions. This indicates that adding the said program in the NBP existing program would result to a positive outcome that will surely help and assist the inmates regardless of the security camps where do they belong.

According to Wedding and Neimic, 2003 said that, the characters and plot can mirror their present life conditions and statuses. The therapist will assist the clients in obtaining understanding, reflection, realization, and techniques in solving their personal problems. The goal of the cinematherapy reflects in study conducted, which includes increasing clients' imagination, expression of emotional release and determining the role models (Marsick, 2010), and identifying problems and generating ideas for growth (Hesley, 2000). As mentioned by Sharp et.al. (2002) said that cinematherapy is not just watching films but requires an in – depth understanding of the films metaphors, the characters portrayed in the film and assisting the client in knowing his or her similarities and differences in terms of the film watched. Added by Turns and Macey, 2015 they mentioned that cinematherapy and play have common purpose because, it allows the participants to project themselves onto others. It can also help discuss some personal issues of a person and instill a hope in the viewers or clients. Indeed, Cinematherapy can be used as a standalone intervention, regardless of the therapist theoretical orientation, and allows for a number of potential uses in the therapeutic process. Cinematherapy is designed to help individuals in moments of crisis. It can help cure anything from an identity crisis to co dependency issues. Movies are more than entertainment, they're self – medication and that Cinematherapy is like bubble bath for the soul. (Nancy Peske and Beverly West, 2000).

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